

BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM, A COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN AND BUILDING SYSTEM FOR HOUSING BLOCKS

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ABSTRACT

BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM is both a computer aided design and building system for the construction of housing blocks with industrialized processes. Housing units are the result of the aggregation of two kinds of space-bars: serving bars (kitchen and bathrooms) and served bars (other functions). The addition of bars gives rise to a multiplicity of flexible housing layouts, generated by the computer system. Linear blocks are a result of the assemblage of housing units. A block's generative process can be carried out autonomously by the computer system or/and in interaction with the user. At each stage of the process, the program checks for possible conflicts between the different subsystems (spaces, building services, structure and circulation). Facade compositions can be created in an interactive way, modifying the design parameters (orientation, isolation, illumination and cost). Finally, the program automatically generates the documents for the building of a block (drawings, preliminary estimate). In the future, the computer program will be integrated in a comprehensive web environment, which will facilitate communication and the collaboration among all agents involved in the design and construction of housing.

Keywords: Computer-aided design and building, component based construction, mass housing

1. MASS HOUSING AND ICT

In today's industrialized countries, there is a need for flexible, industrially produced dwellings, which respond to social (family restructuring, multi/intercultural societies), economic (part-time jobs, working at home, women at work) and technological (prefabrication, sustainability, ICT) demands. In this context of change, the problem of housing must be rethought once again, in order to create dwellings meeting the challenges of our time. We need versatile layouts, which allow transformations during the daytime to facilitate working at home, and that can become larger or smaller as the number of occupants varies over the years. In our increasingly dismembered societies, we have the possibility of promoting community values by providing people with shared spaces in buildings. In order to make buildings sustainable, we should use construction systems which make components maintenance and replacement easier (partitions, facades, technical services). And, to achieve all of these goals, it is possible to apply technological means throughout the whole process: from design and construction (use of ICT to support the design process, prefabrication, robotics), to performance (energy control), and maintenance (facilities management).

In this scenario, ICT have the capacity of becoming a decisive transformation factor, providing computerized environments to support the design and construction of housing, according to the social, economic and technological needs of our time. Such is the ultimate purpose of BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM: to create an environment which supports the design and construction of housing blocks with flexible dwellings, using industrial components and assembled according to the principles of open prefabrication.

2. INTERTWINING OF ARCHITECTURAL AND COMPUTER-AIDED DESIGN SYSTEMS

BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM (<http://www.barcodehousing.net>) is both an architectural system based on prefabricated components and a computer-aided building and design system. At the outset, our strategy was to link both systems, as the earliest applications of computers to architecture, like OXSYS or HARNESS, had done. The benefit of this approach was, as Cross pointed out, that “Instead of the virtually infinite freedom of design in traditional building, the architect working with system building was constrained within a system boundary which could also be managed by the machine” (Cross 1976).

In our case, however, we have created both the architectural and the computer-aided design systems from scratch. We did not go through a process of knowledge elicitation to extract rules from a given building system to then translate them into the computer, as the designers of OXSYS did (Eastman 1999, p. 59). Rather, rules were already present in the conception of the architectural system. As a matter of fact, it would be rather difficult to distinguish one system from the other, since they are intimately related. Nevertheless, for purely descriptive purposes, we will describe them separately.

Therefore, BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM consists of two intertwined systems:

1. An architectural system, with housing layouts conceived as aggregations of space-bars which are then grouped into linear blocks. Construction is based on industrially produced components, assembled according to principles of open prefabrication.
2. A computer-aided design system which allows users to explore formal and spatial configurations of housing units and blocks individually and in collaboration, in interaction with the system.

3. ARCHITECTURAL SYSTEM

The architectural system can be described in two ways: as a spatial system and as a building system.

3.1. Spatial system

A grid is a fundamental component in the designing process of a modular system. Its purpose is both to define spaces as well as the positioning of physical elements (Habraken 1976). BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM is based on a 120 cm. grid. This module was adopted because it proved to be the most adequate to create well-dimensioned spaces (e.g. 240 cm. makes a kitchen with two working surfaces; a

bathroom with three pieces aligned on one side); it was the right width for the pre-cast slabs, and an adequate dimension for facade panels and openings.

Based on this grid, the modular spatial components are assembled in two different levels: 1. Space-bars are assembled to create housing units (Figure 1) 2. Housing units are put together to make a block (Figure 2).

Housing units

Housing units are the result of aggregating space-bars of one and two modules 120 cm. wide and 840 cm. long. For each width, there are two kinds of bars: serving bars, including kitchen, bathroom and building services; and served bars, adjacent spaces which can be used for any other purpose (eating, sleeping, working). While the dimensions of rooms in serving bars are constrained by the objects they contain (kitchen and bathroom equipment, bathroom, downspouts and ducts), spaces created by joining served bars can have flexible dimensions.

Flexibility is a characteristic of this spatial system. There is no standard-unit for a standard-occupant. Rather, each unit can be configured differently combining space-bars to fit the needs of their inhabitants. It is possible to create rooms in a given spatial arrangement in multiple ways, by means of mobile partitions. Furthermore, housing units can increase or decrease in size, adding and lending space-bars to and from adjacent units. This way, housing units can adapt to the changing occupants and their living conditions throughout the building's life.

Figure 1. Generation of housing units.

Figure 2. Generation of blocks.

Blocks

They are the result of the aggregation of housing units. This notwithstanding, a 'block' is considered as a separate system, independent from the units. To provide access to the units in a multi-story arrangement, a 'block' has a circulation system, consisting of open staircases located at the interstices between units and connected to open walkways. Also, since the housing units are not self-bearing, the 'block' must provide a structure to house them. In this regard, a 'block' becomes a 'support structure', as defined by Habraken: "A construction which allows the provision of dwellings which can be built, altered and taken down, independently of the others" (Habraken 1972, pp. 59-60).

3.2 Building system

The building system is based on open prefabrication methods, using components from different manufacturers. The main structural system is made up of pre-cast reinforced concrete members, with girders spanning 480 and 600 cm. Floor slabs are made of pre-stressed concrete plates, 120 cm. wide and 840 cm. long. A secondary structural system for walkways and staircases is made of steel and anchored to the concrete structure.

Building services run outside the block, under the walkways, entering the housing unit at the serving bars, through the suspended ceiling. This way, any service can be easily accessible from the outside and from the inside of the apartment, facilitating maintenance.

Ventilated facades are built with resin panels and, eventually, solar panels. This layered facade, with an air gap, provides a good isolation both in winter and summertime. In the front facade, light protection is achieved with perforated panels and in the service facade by the shadow cast by walkways.

3.3 Intertwining of spatial and building systems.

In order to define an architectural system, besides defining the characteristics of each subsystem, it is essential to establish the relationships between them. For instance, in the configuration of the housing unit, the relations of the spatial components (serving and served space-bars) with the structure are implicit: columns can only be placed in the serving bars, but not in the served ones. Also, building services only run vertically through the serving bars, which already have a provision of spaces to contain ducts and pipes. This way, conflicts between living spaces and structure (e.g. interrupting a glazed facade with a column) or between living spaces and building services (e.g. providing an opening for a waste stack in a living area) are prevented.

4. COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN AND BUILDING SYSTEM

In a draft for a proposal of a computer system presented in 1998, Habraken wrote: "Finding ways to make the computer truly participate in designing and not just be a glorified drafting tool, has been a long term concern for me. The problem is not primarily one of programming. It is one of knowing about designing. We must first be able to tell the machine what to do and what to understand" (Habraken 1998).

Precisely, this was our goal as we were designing the architectural system: to come up with some design principles which could be easily moved onto the computer. In our case, however, there was no clear cut between *designing* and *programming* the system. For instance, by thinking the floor-plan as an aggregation of space-bars we pursued two goals simultaneously: to create flexible dwellings, but also, to conceive a plan in a way that would facilitate the subsequent application of space allocation techniques. This way, rules did not have to be extracted from a previously existing building system. Rather, rules were already present in the conception of the architectural system, so architectural design and computation became deeply interwoven: design principles were tested against computer procedures before committing to a particular decision, and, conversely, ad hoc procedures were used during the design of the architectural system (for instance, to search for the most appropriate width for space-bars).

As architects, our role has been to design an architectural system, rather than a particular building. We have played the role of ‘system designers’, rather than ‘end designers’ (Gross 1996). After the rules and constraints implicit in the architectural system were made explicit to the computer, a user interacting with the program would be able to unfold the potential of the architectural system, visualizing particular solutions; a visualization which, incidentally, could only be performed over the computer. In other words, the ontological existence of the architectural system could only be proved after its computerized version was ‘activated’ on the computer.

In its current implementation, BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM can be described as a procedural system operating on a finite number of spatial and building components. The generative process takes place at three different levels, in this sequence: housing units generating; blocks assembling and facades composition.

4.1 Housing unit generating

Many computer-aided building models, particularly those based on components, tend to think of a building as the assembly of physical objects in space. Such was the view adopted, for instance, by one of the pioneer systems, the SSHA started by Aart Bijl in 1969, where symbols representing walls, windows and doors were placed in the drawing, and then the spaces bounded by them were extracted (Eastman 1999, pp. 48-53). A later development of OXSYS, named BDS, sought to reconcile object and spatial representation, storing building components and spaces in separate modules (Hoskins 1979). In our case, we have given priority to space over form. The building blocks of BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM are spatial elements. Partition elements are determined after the spatial configuration, rather than the other way around.

The generation process of a housing unit is divided into two stages: 1. Production of all possible space-bar combinations fitting within a given rectangular area, and 2. Construction of proper layouts for each space-bar arrangement. The first part of the process is an exhaustive search of the solutions space, which can be automatically performed after setting a few constraints. The second one is a trial and error process seeking a valid solution. This division strategy, which has the purpose of avoiding combinatorial explosions and optimizing the search process, is akin to the one proposed by Steadman and then implemented by Mitchell et al (Steadman 1983, p.157).

4.1.1. Space-bars arrangement

In the first stage of the floor-plan generating, space-bars arrangements are created for a given rectangular area. The process begins after setting the surface (sq. m.) and the number of occupants. Given the limited number of arrangements, it is possible to perform an exhaustive search of the solutions space, using an Iterative Deepening Search (IDS) procedure. A spatial allocation procedure is used to find out all the possible space bars combinations within the given rectangular area, which fulfil the following constraints: 1. A rectangular arrangement must contain at least a double-module serving-bar 2. Serving and served bars are placed alternatively 3. If the number of occupants is larger than four, the layout must contain two serving-bars. The first constraint guarantees that any housing unit will have at least a kitchen and a bathroom. The second, prevents two serving-bars from being adjacent, in order to avoid a concentration of services and favouring the creation of versatile spaces by the

subsequent layout generator procedure. The third one ensures the number of bathrooms is the one required for the number of occupants.

4.1.2. Layout generating

The goal of the second stage of the floor-plan generating process is to create spatial layouts, accomplishing the conditions established in the constraint model. A spatial allocation procedure is used for generating valid layouts for a given space-bar arrangement. In order to do that, the vertical arrangement is first divided horizontally into three zones (Habraken 1976). The resulting rectangular cells will then be assigned a specific function (kitchen, bathroom) or, alternatively, they will be used as spatial units to build multifunctional spaces.

Figure 3. User interface for housing unit layouts.

Figure 4. User interface to create blocks.

This second stage is based on a heuristic method which guides the search process. There are four different procedures involved, executed in the following order. First, the kitchen is inserted. It has to lie inside a double-module serving bar, in an area next to the walkway. Second, the living areas are built up, next to the kitchen, and also facing the walkway. This second procedure creating the living area, checks for available spaces on the left and right sides of the kitchen, choosing the largest free space. With the third procedure, bathrooms are placed. The orientation of the bathroom doors and their position considers the flanking living spaces, to avoid undesired visual contacts. Finally, with the fourth procedure, bedrooms are built with the remaining cells unused by serving and served bars. It starts by taking a cell inside a serving space-bar, to make it grow towards the left and right sides.

The interface to visualize the floor-plans is simple and straightforward (Figure 3). With a set of sliders, it is possible to search through the solutions space for valid plans. As Petrovic noticed, a user interacting with this kind of system is not able to distinguish between ‘designing’ and ‘selecting’ (Petrovic 1998).

4.2 Block assembling

Blocks are the result of assembling a set of housing units in a previously defined volume. A block is generated in two steps: first, stairs are placed; then, housing units are inserted. Both generation processes are based on Best First Search techniques. At a particular level of the state-action tree, determined by a configurable value of depth K, the procedure evaluates the solution according to heuristic methods, and then backtracks to find the ‘best’ path to reach that solution.

4.2.1 Staircases

The process to place staircases begins after the creation of the volumetric envelope. Separation between staircases, and maximum and minimum distances from the housing unit to the stair, comply with local building codes. Accordingly, a procedure is used to place the staircases in such a way as to guarantee that each housing unit will be accessible through walkways.

4.2.2. Housing units

The insertion of housing units begins after the staircases have been placed. At each insertion, the system makes sure of the following: 1. There is enough space to place the unit 2. Columns go through a serving space-bar 3. Distance to staircase is less than the maximum allowed and 4. There is a serving bar above and below the unit for the building services to pass through.

The process of placing units in the block can be performed automatically or, alternatively, it can be guided by the user by means of a diagram consisting of a set of sliders to position the insertion node and to select the housing units (Figure 4). If the user attempts to insert a unit in a place where there would be a conflict with the structure or which does not comply with the vertical alignment of building services, the system will reject it. In both cases, with or without the intervention of the user, the rules and constraints controlling the process are the same. This way, the user can interrupt the automated process to gain control or, alternatively, it can start it and then let the computer continue. This fosters a certain symbiosis between users and computer system (Negroponte 1970).

4.3 Facades composition

The facade is conceived as a system of its own, independent from the block. For each block there can be an unlimited number of facades. In the current implementation, the composition procedure is limited to the front facade. It is designed by the user in interaction with the system using two interfaces to arrange panels and openings and give colour to panels respectively.

The first interface is a set of connected circles (Figure 5), each one controlling the values of a design parameter: orientation, illumination, colour, acoustics and cost. As the user modifies the values the facade composition changes accordingly. For instance, if the facade is oriented to the south, the panel's colour becomes lighter, since dark colours would absorb more solar radiation. Moreover, it is possible to establish a link between design parameters, simply by pulling a line connecting the centres of two circles. Thus, if orientation is linked with illumination, when the orientation changes, the amount of glazed surfaces will increase or decrease, depending on if the facade is oriented towards the north or towards the south.

The second interface consists of a set of sliders, with which the colour distribution can be changed horizontally (all panels in the selected story can change colour at once), vertically (setting control points for the colour distribution across stories) and by housing units (all units of the same size can be assigned the same colour).

Figure 5. User interface to compose facades.

Figure 6. Graphic documentation and cost estimates.

With this sort of interfaces, a facade is designed by acting on the internal structure of its composition, rather than through the direct manipulation of its visual appearance. The interface, in this case, stands for a diagram of the facade, which makes the internal relationships ruling the composition intelligible to the user. It is a sort of representation which has no counterpart in other media, aside from the computer.

4.4 Documentation

As a final step in the generating process, the system automatically generates a 1:200 representation of the block (plans, elevation, and axonometric view) on an A3 sheet (Figure 6). The documentation includes a preliminary estimate, indicating the list of components (e.g. number and type of structural elements, facade panels and windows) necessary to build the block. All the components necessary for constructing a block can be retrieved from the database by reading an index codified as a barcode, drawn at the lower right corner of the sheet.

4.5 System architecture

The building model is made up of five components: kernel, structure, circulation, building services and facade. The data structure in all five modules is a two-dimensional array. This data structure was already used in the earliest computer-aided building systems. The two-dimensional array, as Mitchell wrote, was a “simple but powerful” representation for plans “because it effectively utilizes the structure of the array itself to implicitly represent positions and adjacencies of spatial elements” (Mitchell 1977, p.166). In the seventies, the functionality of a two-dimensional array was severely limited by the memory and speed of the computers; a limitation which today is no longer relevant, particularly in our case, as the number of cells making up the largest block is rather limited.

The system architecture is made up of different layers. At the bottom layer there is the basic data, objects and relations. The five modules make the system layer. The logical layer contains the procedures to generate housing units, blocks and facades, as well as the visualization procedures. At the front-end, there are the user interfaces for housing units, blocks and facades. This structure has been specifically designed for this system to optimize the processes of querying and modifying the building model.

5. WEB-BASED COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT

Already in 1969, in a report of the Building Research Station, one could read that “Use of centralized computer-based project file will enable much closer coordination of the work of specialists, and will allow specialists to collaborate on a continuous rather than an intermittent basis throughout the project” (Mitchell 1977, p.107). Later, it had to be acknowledged that integrated systems would not be capable of improving coordination (Richens 1983, D’Arcy 1986). Nowadays, following the widespread of Internet, the early goals have been restated, putting more emphasis on collaboration than coordination: “The process will not be completely linear, as it is now, nor will it be parallel, because the solutions provided by one collaborator serve as input, or at least as guidelines, to others. The envisioned process will be fluid, dynamically negotiated, and mutually stimulated –providing the participants with a greater stake in the results and therefore a greater commitment to its success” (Kalay 2004, p. 416).

Even though in its current implementation BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM is a stand-alone application, the ultimate purpose of which is its integration in a web-based environment, to promote the collaboration of all agents involved in the design and construction process of mass housing: architects, occupants, builders and administrators. A first step in this direction has already been done implementing an environment to visualize blocks created by the core system.

Other functionalities, which will allow all participants to intervene throughout the design, construction and maintenance stages, are to be implemented in a nearby future. Then, the process of placing housing units to make a block would be done collaboratively, on the web. This way, the ‘design’ of the block would be the result of the sum of individual decisions. In this scenario, the architect would become a mediator in a collaborative design process, whose task would be to guide the system towards the creation of meaningful results.

Also, this open design process should have an impact on construction. Building companies should be able to check the on-going design and make proposals for facade components, for instance. Orders for prefabricated structural components could be launched directly from the building model, without the mediation of drawings. All of this is feasible from the technology point of view, but we are well aware of the fact that transforming building practices does not depend exclusively on the possibilities of technology alone.

6. CONCLUSIONS

After the pioneering works of the sixties and seventies, application of computers to design and construction seems to have followed three different paths of development, not necessarily separated. The most effective until now, has been to use computers to perform specific tasks within already existing practices (drawing plans and renderings, for instance). The second and more difficult way of practical implementation is to create design and building systems based upon generic, comprehensive building model descriptions, encompassing the whole process of design, construction and maintenance of the building (Eastman 1999, p. 31). This is still an unfulfilled goal stemming from the early integrated systems. The third one is to unfold all of computer’s potential in specific projects and/or in particular practices, to achieve the

deepest integration between architecture and computation. This goes beyond pure drafting and modelling, but is lacking the more ambitious goal of establishing generic building systems. BAR_CODE HOUSING SYSTEM belongs to this third path of development.

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